

SONOGRAPHIC EVALUATION OF ECTOPIC PREGNANCY IN HYPERTENSIVE AND DIABETIC PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background:

Sonographic evaluation of ectopic pregnancy is critical for early diagnosis, especially in patients with chronic conditions like hypertension and diabetes. These comorbidities may complicate clinical presentation and increase the risk of adverse maternal outcomes. High-resolution ultrasound offers a non-invasive, reliable method to identify ectopic implantation and guide timely management.

Objective: To evaluate the role of sonography in ectopic pregnancy of diabetes and hypertensive patients.

Method: This cross-sectional study was conducted on women of reproductive age presenting with clinical suspicion of ectopic pregnancy. Participants having a verified history of diabetes mellitus and/or hypertension were included. High-resolution ultrasound equipment was used to perform transabdominal and transvaginal sonographic examinations after a thorough clinical evaluation and laboratory investigations. Sonographic measures were recorded, including the characteristics of the adnexal mass, the presence of the gestational sac and fetal heart activity. The results were examined to identify the sonographic patterns of ectopic pregnancy in individuals with diabetes and hypertension, as well as to evaluate associations with biochemical markers and clinical profiles.

Results: Out of 22 ectopic pregnancies participants evaluated from sonographic evaluation only 6 (27.27%) patients were found hypertensive while on the other hand 2 (9.09%) diabetic patients were among 22 ectopic pregnancies participants. Sonographic evaluation revealed different types of ectopic pregnancies comprises of 4 (18.18%) corneal EP, 4 (18.18) uterine EP and 14 (63.64%) others EP (including Ampulla EP, Abdominal EP, Cervical EP, and Ovarian EP. Sonographic evaluation also revealed that out of 22 patients, 10 (45.45%) patients contain free fluid while on the other hand 12 (54.55%) patients do not have free fluid. As far as gestational sac is concerned, it was found in 19 (86.36%) patients while 3 (13.64%) patients do not have gestational sac. Cardiac activity was found in 14 (63.64%) patients while 8 (36.36%) patients do not have cardiac activity.

Conclusion; This study demonstrates that sonography remains a highly effective tool for detecting ectopic pregnancy in women with coexisting hypertension and diabetes. Most patients showed identifiable sonographic features, including adnexal masses, gestational sacs, and fetal cardiac activity, enabling timely diagnosis. Although only a small proportion of ectopic pregnancy cases were associated with hypertension and diabetes, recognizing these comorbidities alongside key ultrasound findings can support earlier intervention and improved clinical outcomes:

INTRODUCTION

An ectopic pregnancy refers to any pregnancy that occurs outside of the usual implantation site within the endometrial cavity. Ectopic pregnancy (EP) is a potentially life-threatening condition in which a fertilized ovum implants outside the uterine cavity, most commonly in the fallopian tube (approximately 95% of cases) ^[1]. Globally, ectopic pregnancy comprises 1-2% of all pregnancies. Most recent Pakistani hospital/clinical studies report ectopic pregnancy frequencies between 0.4% and 2.5% of pregnancies ⁽¹⁾.

Ectopic pregnancy poses a significant risk of maternal morbidity and mortality however, early and accurate diagnosis is critical to reduce the risk of tubal rupture, hemorrhage, and subsequent fertility loss. Several risk factors increase its likelihood, including pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), previous ectopic pregnancy, tubal surgery, use of assisted reproductive technologies, and smoking ⁽³⁾. Additionally, intrauterine device (IUD) use and maternal age above 35 years are associated with higher risk. These factors often lead to tubal damage or dysfunction, impairing the transport of the fertilized ovum to the uterus ⁽⁴⁾.

Normally, the egg should implant in the uterine lining, but in an ectopic pregnancy, it usually implants in the fallopian tube, this happens in around 95% of cases, especially in the middle of the tube (known as the ampulla) ⁽⁵⁾. The egg can also attach in the ovary, cervix, uterine corner, or abdomen, albeit this is less often. ⁽⁶⁾ Ectopic pregnancy is exceedingly dangerous and is one of the primary causes of serious health problems, including death, during early pregnancy ^[7]. This is because a developing pregnancy can cause the tube to burst,

resulting in serious internal bleeding. If not treated promptly, this can progress to a potentially lethal condition called as shock. Ectopic pregnancies occur in around 1 to 2 out of every 100 pregnancies, while the true number may be higher because some cases go undocumented or are not recorded ⁽⁸⁾

Ectopic pregnancy is a complicated and possibly life-threatening syndrome that affects 1- 2% of all pregnancies, yet it is one of the major causes of maternal death in the first trimester. In a healthy pregnancy, the egg travels from the ovary down the fallopian tube and adheres to the uterine lining, where it can develop securely. However, with an ectopic pregnancy, this travel is halted ^[9]. The egg becomes trapped, generally in the fallopian tube (a tubal pregnancy), and begins to grow in an environment that cannot support it. The actual cause is frequently unknown; however injury or obstruction in the fallopian tubes is a major contributor. This can be caused by past infections such as pelvic inflammatory disease (particularly Chlamydia trachomatis), tube surgery, or endometriosis.

Other risk factors include a history of ectopic pregnancy, use of assisted reproductive technologies such as IVF, smoking, and age above 35 years ^[10]. The main reason is damage or dysfunction of the tubal cilia and muscular contractions that normally propel the ovum toward the uterine cavity. Conditions such as pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), previous tubal surgery, endometriosis, or congenital tubal abnormalities can lead to scarring, adhesions, or narrowing of the tube ^[11]. These changes impede the normal passage of the fertilized ovum, resulting in tubal implantation. Additionally,

smoking and hormonal imbalances can impair tubal motility, further increasing the risk ^[12]. Ectopic

pregnancies are less common but can occur in the ovary, cervix, uterine corner, or abdominal cavity ^[13].

(18)

Ectopic pregnancy symptoms are differing. Ectopic pregnancy often presents with nonspecific early symptoms that may mimic normal pregnancy or miscarriage ^[14]. The classic triad includes abdominal or pelvic pain, vaginal bleeding, and amenorrhea (missed period). Pain is usually unilateral and may become severe if the fallopian tube ruptures, leading to shoulder tip pain due to diaphragmatic irritation from intra-abdominal bleeding. Other symptoms include dizziness, fainting, nausea, and signs of hypovolemic shock in cases of rupture ¹⁵.

Some patients may experience adnexal tenderness or a palpable pelvic mass during examination. Because symptoms vary and may appear late, early ultrasound and β -hCG testing are essential for diagnosis. Some women may not notice anything strange at first, while others may have intense lower abdomen pain on one side, vaginal bleeding, vertigo, or discomfort in the shoulder (indicating internal hemorrhage) ^[16]. When the fallopian tube ruptures, it is considered a medical emergency and requires rapid treatment to prevent life-threatening bleeding. Early detection is critical, and is typically achieved using transvaginal ultrasound and blood tests that evaluate the

pregnancy hormone (hCG) ^[17]. Sonography (ultrasound) is an important tool for early detection

since it helps determine the position of the pregnancy and assesses the risk of problems ¹⁸.

The diagnosis of ectopic pregnancy relies on a combination of clinical evaluation, biochemical testing, and imaging techniques ^[19]. Clinically, suspicion arises in women of reproductive age presenting with abdominal pain, amenorrhea, and vaginal bleeding ^[20]. The most critical diagnostic tools are transvaginal ultrasonography (TVUS) and serial serum β -human chorionic gonadotropin (β -hCG) measurements. TVUS is the gold standard imaging method, allowing visualization of an adnexal mass, tubal ring, or free fluid in the pelvis, which are highly suggestive of ectopic implantation ^[21]. In a normal intrauterine pregnancy, a gestational sac is typically visible on TVUS when β -hCG levels exceed the discriminatory zone (usually 1500–2000 mIU/mL); absence of an intrauterine sac at this level strongly indicates an ectopic pregnancy ^[22]. Culdocentesis and diagnostic laparoscopy may be used when imaging is inconclusive, with laparoscopy considered the definitive diagnostic and sometimes therapeutic procedure. Early and accurate diagnosis

is essential to prevent tubal rupture and maternal morbidity ^[23]. Transvaginal ultrasonography, in particular, allows for thorough imaging of the uterus and surrounding structures, making it an important tool for detecting ectopic pregnancies early on.

Ectopic pregnancy poses additional diagnostic and management challenges when associated with hypertension or diabetes mellitus. Both conditions can influence maternal physiology, pregnancy outcomes, and imaging findings. In hypertensive women, chronic vascular changes such as vasoconstriction, endothelial dysfunction, and impaired uteroplacental perfusion may exacerbate the risk of tubal ischemia, which can impair the normal transport of the fertilized ovum and predispose to ectopic implantation ^[24]. Furthermore, hypertensive disorders like pre-eclampsia can complicate the clinical course by masking or mimicking symptoms such as abdominal pain and elevated blood pressure during ectopic rupture ^[25]. Similarly, diabetes mellitus has been associated with altered tubal motility, delayed ovum transport, and hormonal imbalances that increase susceptibility to ectopic gestation ^[26]. Poor glycemic control can lead to microangiopathy affecting the fallopian tubes, and diabetic women are often at higher risk for infections, including pelvic inflammatory disease, which is a known predisposing factor for ectopic pregnancy ^[27]. Moreover, diabetes may also complicate the management of ectopic pregnancy by influencing anesthetic risk, wound healing, and metabolic stability during surgical intervention or methotrexate therapy (28).

In hypertensive patients, the primary concern is hemodynamic instability resulting from tubal rupture and internal hemorrhage. These patients require strict blood pressure monitoring and the use of antihypertensive medications compatible with pregnancy, such as labetalol or hydralazine, to prevent end-organ damage during the acute phase ^[26]. If surgical intervention is required, anesthetic and intraoperative management should minimize cardiovascular stress. Moreover, women with preeclampsia or chronic hypertension are at increased risk for postoperative complications like poor wound healing or renal dysfunction, necessitating close postoperative observation ⁽²⁷⁾.

For diabetic patients, management focuses on maintaining optimal glycemic control to prevent complications related to infection, delayed wound healing, and metabolic instability. Perioperative insulin therapy or adjusted oral hypoglycemic regimens may be required based on glucose monitoring. Medical management with methotrexate, a folate antagonist used in early unruptured ectopic pregnancies, should be used cautiously, as hepatic dysfunction and impaired glucose metabolism can influence its pharmacokinetics ^[29]. In diabetic women, infection prevention and nutritional optimization are crucial following surgical or medical treatment. Transvaginal ultrasonography (TVUS) and serial β -hCG testing are used for diagnosis and follow-up.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A Descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted. 22 ectopic pregnancies with diabetes and hypertension data were collected from University of Lahore Teaching Hospital in 4 months. Female patients aged 18 years and above with suspected ectopic pregnancy were included while non-confirmed ectopic pregnancy, Molar or multiple pregnancies were excluded. Transabdominal and/or transvaginal ultrasound were performed using Ultrasound machine GE company S8 model. The process was properly described and consent obtained. If a trans-abdominal scan is required, the patient was advised to consume water and maintain a full bladder. The patient was instructed to empty her bladder before undergoing a trans-vaginal scan. The patient was then made comfortable on the exam table. To improve picture clarity, a gel is administered to the lower abdomen or transvaginal probe. The scan was performed softly, and the patient's comfort was maintained throughout the procedure. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive analysis was used to assess data distribution. Continuous data was summarized using mean and standard deviation, whilst categorical variables will be analyzed using frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

Out of 22 ectopic pregnancies participants evaluated from sonographic evaluation only 6 (27.27%)

patients were found hypertensive while on the other hand 2 (9.09%) diabetic patients were among 22 ectopic pregnancies participants as shown in Table 1. Sonographic evaluation revealed different types of ectopic pregnancies comprises of 4 (18.18%) cornual EP, 4 (18.18) uterine EP and 14 (63.64%) others EP (including Ampulla EP, Abdominal EP, Cervical EP, and Ovarian EP) as shown in Table 2. Sonographic evaluation also revealed that out of 22 patients, 10 (45.45%) patients contain free fluid while on the

other hand 12 (54.55%) patients do not have free fluid. As far as gestational sac is concerned, it was found in 19 (86.36%) patients while 3 (13.64%) patients do not have gestational sac. Cardiac activity was found in 14 (63.64%) patients while 8 (36.36%) patients do not have cardiac activity. Sonographic evaluation of all participants included in study is shown in Fig

Table 1: Frequency of Hypertensive and Diabetic Patients

Variables	Number	Frequency
Hypertensive	6	27.27%
Diabetic	2	9.09%
Non-Hypertensive and Non-Diabetic	14	63.64%
Total	22	100.0%

We take 22 patients out of 22 6 was hypertensive and 2 was diabetic and the remaining 16 patients are non hypertensive and diabetic in table 1.

Table 2: Frequency of Types of Ectopic Pregnancies

Ectopic Pregnancy	Number	Frequency
Cornual	4	18.18%
Uterine	4	18.18%
Other	14	63.64%
Total	22	100.0%

22 ectopic patients are taken 4 was get cornul 4 get uterine and the remaining have other like ampulla Tubal

A complex mass noted in left adnexal region. It measures 30mm * 34mm It contains a gestational sac in its central part. Mild amount of free fluid noted in abdomen and pelvis. These findings are suggestive of

ruptured left tubal ectopic pregnancy with mild haemoperitoneum.

A complex mass noted in right adnexal region. It measures mm x mm. It contains a gestational sac in its central part. Moderate amount of free fluid noted in abdomen and pelvis. Haematoma formation noted in pelvis. These findings are suggestive of ruptured right tubal ectopic pregnancy with moderate haemoperitoneum.

association between these comorbidities and the risk of ectopic pregnancy.

Sonographic evaluation revealed varying types of ectopic pregnancies, with the majority classified as “other” types (63.64%), including ampullary, abdominal, cervical, and ovarian locations. Cornual and uterine ectopic pregnancies each accounted for 18.18% of cases. These findings align with the general epidemiologic trend indicating that the ampullary region of the fallopian tube is the most common site of implantation (approximately 70–80%). The detection of rare sites such as abdominal and cervical ectopic pregnancies underscores the importance of comprehensive sonographic assessment to ensure accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.

DISCUSSION:

The present study aimed to evaluate ectopic pregnancies sonographically with a focus on their occurrence among hypertensive and diabetic patients. Out of 22 participants diagnosed with ectopic pregnancy, 6 (27.27%) were hypertensive and 2 (9.09%) were diabetic. These findings suggest that while hypertension and diabetes are not direct causes of ectopic pregnancy, their coexistence may influence the clinical presentation and complications associated with ectopic gestation. Previous studies have reported that women with chronic medical conditions such as hypertension and diabetes may experience altered vascular and hormonal profiles that could impact implantation sites and tubal motility. However, further large-scale studies are needed to establish any statistically significant

The presence of free fluid was observed in 10 (45.45%) patients, which may indicate tubal rupture or internal bleeding, a common sonographic finding in advanced or complicated ectopic pregnancies. The absence of free fluid in 54.55% of patients suggests that early detection was possible in nearly half of the cases, highlighting the critical role of timely ultrasound evaluation in preventing morbidity and mortality.

Regarding gestational sac visualization, 86.36% of patients had a detectable sac, while 13.64% did not. This is consistent with prior research showing that the visualization of a gestational sac depends on the gestational age and the degree of tubal distention. Similarly, cardiac activity was found in 63.64% of cases, which suggests that a significant number of ectopic pregnancies were viable at the time of examination. This finding emphasizes the importance of careful sonographic monitoring to distinguish between viable and non-viable ectopic pregnancies, as this can influence treatment decisions such as medical versus surgical intervention.

Overall, the results of this study reinforce the utility of ultrasonography as a first-line, noninvasive diagnostic tool in evaluating ectopic pregnancies, even in patients with coexisting systemic disorders like hypertension and diabetes. Although the sample size was limited, the findings highlight the need for increased awareness among clinicians to perform early and detailed sonographic assessments in high-risk groups to reduce complications.

The present study highlights the crucial role of sonographic evaluation in the diagnosis and characterization of ectopic pregnancies, particularly among patients with coexisting medical conditions such as hypertension and diabetes. Among the 22 patients with ectopic pregnancy, 27.27% were hypertensive and 9.09% were diabetic, suggesting that while these comorbidities were not predominant, they may still influence maternal outcomes and the diagnostic process.

Sonographic findings revealed a diversity of ectopic pregnancy locations, with the majority (63.64%) classified as "other types" including ampullary, abdominal, cervical, and ovarian pregnancies, while cornual and uterine ectopic pregnancies each accounted for 18.18% of cases. The detection of free fluid in 45.45% of participants indicated the possibility of rupture or hemoperitoneum, underscoring the importance of early diagnosis. Furthermore, gestational sacs were visualized in 86.36% of patients and cardiac activity in 63.64%, confirming ultrasound as a reliable method for evaluating the viability and progression of ectopic pregnancies.

Overall, the study concludes that sonography is an indispensable, non-invasive, and highly sensitive diagnostic tool for the early detection and assessment of ectopic pregnancy. Timely sonographic evaluation can significantly reduce morbidity and mortality by guiding appropriate medical or surgical intervention, particularly in high-risk patients with underlying hypertension or diabetes.

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